

Cyclisation of Ethyl Acetoacetate and Benzoylacetate with Arylamines in Presence of Polyphosphoric Acid

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Manuscript received 14 September 1974; accepted 5 February 1975

Cyclisation of ethyl acetoacetate with *o*- and *m*-nitroanilines has been effected for the first time using polyphosphoric acid to give 4-hydroxynitroquinaldines. 2-Methyl- and -2-phenyl-4-hydroxyquinolines have been obtained in very high yields from ethylacetoacetate and benzoylacetate with arylamines by a method using PPA.

MANY unsuccessful attempts were made to obtain 8-nitro-4-hydroxyquinaldine, an intermediate for 8-alkylaminoantimalarials, from *o*-nitroanilin and ethyl acetoacetate by Conrad-Limpach method, the presence of the *o*-nitrogroup interfering with the reaction¹. The same method using ethyl benzoylacetate and arylamines for the synthesis of 6-methoxy- and 7-methoxy-2-phenyl-4-hydroxyquinolines, important intermediates for highly active 4-alkylamino-antimalarials, also met with little success². Cyclisation of β -arylamino-cinnamates with acetic anhydride-sulphuric acid was fairly successful³. The direct synthesis of 2-phenyl-4-hydroxyquinolines (yield 35-40%) from arylamines and the β -keto ester was achieved using polyphosphoric acid at 150°, but with *p*-nitroaniline the yield of the 4-hydroxyquinoline was only 5.4%⁴. Arylamines with a nitrogroup ortho or meta to the amino-group, even in the presence of the activating methoxy or methyl groups in the molecule, failed to condense with ethyl acetoacetate in the presence of PPA.⁵

In the present work, the method applied previously⁴⁻⁶ using PPA has been modified to cyclise ethyl acetoacetate with *o*- and *m*-nitroanilines for the first time giving 8-nitro- and 7-nitro-4-hydroxyquinaldines (yields 55 and 59%), ethyl benzoylacetate with *p*-nitroanilin giving 2-phenyl-6-nitro-4-hydroxyquinoline (41.5%), and improving quantitatively the yields (60-95%) of 2-phenyl- and 2-methyl-4-hydroxyquinolines from aniline, *o*-, *m*- and *p*-toluidines, *o*-, *m*- and *p*-chloroanilines, *o*- and *p*-anisidines and -phenetidines, 1,3,4- and 1,4,5-xylidines and 1- and 2-naphthylamines.

The direct synthesis of 4-hydroxyquinolines is a two-step process: (i) a slow stage of anil formation at lower temperature, and (ii) a fast stage of ring-closure at higher temperature. Instead of heating the mixture of arylamine, β -keto ester and PPA directly at 150° or 170° as in the previous work, the slow stage is given sufficient time in the modified

method by initiating preparation of a crude crotonate or a cinnamate which easily gets cyclised at higher temperature giving clean products in quantitative yields. Ethyl acetoacetate gets cyclised with arylamines more easily than benzoylacetate because of the greater reactivity of the acetyl group than that of the benzoyl group, the former forming anils more readily.⁷

Experimental

Preparation of PPA :

Phosphorous pentoxide (20 g) was dissolved into orthophosphoric acid (12 ml; $d = 1.75$) by heating the mixture at 90° for $\frac{1}{2}$ hr; more pentoxide (5-6 g) was added to the solution and the mixture heated further for $\frac{1}{2}$ hr at 90°, scum undissolved being removed. The clear syrupy solution was used for each experiment.

8-Nitro-4-hydroxyquinaldine

A mixture of *o*-nitroaniline (3 g), freshly crystallised and ethyl acetoacetate (4 g), freshly distilled, with a trace of iodine, was heated on steam-bath for $3\frac{1}{4}$ hr, and then kept over calcium chloride for six days (crotonates not containing a nitrogroup were not thus kept). The crude crotonate, cooled with ice externally, was mixed with PPA and stirred for $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. After heating the reaction mass to 80° with effervescence, it was kept for 24 hrs in a desiccator; it was subsequently heated to 150°-160° very slowly over 2 hr. After neutralisation on the acidic side, yellow product separated; it was dissolved in dilute alkali giving orange solution and precipitated with acetic acid (2.27 g; yield 55%; m.p. 225°-230°), yellow feathery crystals from aqueous ethanol; m.p. 233°-234°; lit.¹ m.p. 224°-230°. Its ethanol solution gave orange coloration with ferric chloride (Found: N, 13.62. $C_{10}H_8O_3N_2$ requires N, 13.72).

8-Nitro-4-chloroquinaldine

The above product (0.5 g) was refluxed with phosphorous oxychloride (8 ml) for $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. The solution was treated with ice and neutralised with ammonia; the product was crystallised from ethanol; yellowish needles; m.p. 112°–113°, lit.¹ m.p. 111°–113° (Found : N, 12.50; Cl, 15.80; C₁₀H₇O₂N₂Cl requires N, 12.58; Cl, 15.91).

7-Nitro-4-hydroxyquinaldine

A mixture of *m*-nitroaniline (3 g) and ethyl acetoacetate (4 g) was worked up as before. The yellow product (2.65 g; 59.2%; m.p. 305°–310°), soluble in alkali giving deep yellow solution, was purified by alkali (norit) and acetic acid treatment (m.p. 315°–318°). It was insoluble in water, slightly soluble in ethanol and sparingly in acetic acid. With ferric chloride, it gave orange coloration (Found : N, 13.75. C₁₀H₉O₃N₂ requires N, 13.72).

The second product, alkali insoluble, (1 g) was identified as *m*-nitroanilin, m.p. 114°.

The chloro derivative, obtained by refluxing the above 4-hydroxyquinaldine with phosphorous oxychloride was crystallised from aqueous ethanol, m.p. 93°–94°. (Found : N, 12.61; Cl, 15.92. C₁₀H₇N₂O₂Cl requires N, 12.58; Cl, 15.91). Halcrow and Kermach¹ reported m.p. of 5-nitro-4-chloroquinaldine 111°–113°. Hence, the above 4-hydroxyquinaldine should be 7-nitro-4-hydroxyquinaldine.

6-Nitro-4-hydroxyquinaldine

(a) A mixture of *p*-nitroaniline (3.5 g) and the ester (4.5 g) was worked up as before. The yellow product (3.94 g, yield 77.2%) was purified by alkali and acetic acid (m.p. > 400°). It gave orange coloration with ferric chloride. Mallams and Israelstam⁵ reported m.p. 400° and lit.⁸ gave m.p. > 400°. The m.p. of 6-nitro-4-chloroquinaldine was found 141°–142°; lit. reported 146°–148°⁶ and 142°.⁸

(b) 6-Nitro-4-hydroxyquinaldine was also obtained by the nitration of 4-hydroxyquinaldine (0.6 g) with sodium nitrate (1.5 g) in PPA, by stirring the mixture at 5°–10° for $\frac{1}{2}$ hr, at room temperature for 1 hr and raising the temperature 70°–80°; when on treatment with water and norit, the filtrate on neutralisation gave yellow product (0.67 g, yield 87%, m.p. > 400°). Its chloroderivative was found to melt at 142°; its mixed m.p. with 6-nitro-4-chloroquinaldine (a) showed no depression.

2-Phenyl-6-nitro-4-hydroxyquinoline

A mixture of *p*-nitroaniline (3 g) and ethyl benzoylacetate (6 g) with a trace of iodine was heated on steam-bath for $\frac{3}{4}$ hr and the mixture was kept in a desiccator for six days. The crude cinnamate was mixed with PPA and worked up as before; the pale yellow product (2.42 g; yield 41.5%) was crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 328°–329°; lit.⁴ reported m.p. 328°–330° and yield 5.4%.

On refluxing with a mixture of phosphorous oxychloride and pentachloride, it gave pale yellow needles (ethanol) m.p. 168°–169°; lit.⁴ m.p. 168°–169°. (Found : Cl, 12.32. C₁₅H₉N₂O₂Cl requires Cl, 12.47).

2-Phenyl-6-methoxy-4-hydroxyquinoline

A mixture of *p*-anisidine and the β -keto ester (each 0.025 mole) was worked up as before. The product (3.85 g, 61%) was crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 288°; lit. reported^{3,2}, m.p. 306°–307° and 287°–290°. Ethanol solution gave red coloration with ferric chloride. The m.p. of 2-phenyl-6-methoxy-4-chloroquinoline, obtained by refluxing with phosphorous oxychloride was found 109°; lit.^{2,3} 109°–110°. (Found : Cl, 13.0. C₁₆H₁₂NOCl requires Cl, 13.1).

1-Hydroxy-3-phenyl-benzo(f)quinoline

A mixture of 2-naphthylamine and the β -keto ester (each 0.025 mole) was worked up as before. The product (5.23 g, 77.2%) was crystallised from ethanol (m.p. 312°) lit.³ m.p. 300° (dec.). Ethanolic solution gave red coloration with ferric chloride.

Its chloroderivative was found to melt at 114°–115°, lit.³ m.p. 114°–115°. (Found : Cl, 12.9. C₁₉H₁₃NCl requires Cl, 12.8).

4-Hydroxy-2-phenyl-benzo(h)quinoline

A mixture of 1-naphthylamine and the β -keto ester (each 0.025 mole) was worked up as before. The product (4.30 g, 63.5%) was crystallised from ethanol; m.p. 211°–212°. Ethanol solution gave red coloration with ferric chloride. (Found : N, 5.38; C₁₉H₁₄NO requires N, 5.4). M.P. of its chloroderivative 116°. (Found : Cl, 12.75. C₁₉H₁₃NCl requires Cl, 12.8).

Acknowledgement

One of us (KD) thanks the college authority for research facilities given to her.

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